

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF DATA COMPOUNDS (4)*

Code no.	R	X	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Biological activity**			
						ALD ₅₀ (mg/kg)	SMA	Loss of R.R.	
AK-1	Methyl	Dimethylamino	C ₇ H ₁₂ SN ₄ O	186–87	83	>1 000	214	157	–
AK-2	Ethyl	Dimethylamino	C ₉ H ₁₄ SN ₄ O	78–80	80	>1 000	207	142	+
AK-3	Propyl	Dimethylamino	C ₉ H ₁₆ SN ₄ O	160–62	75	681	205	139	+
AK-4	Methyl	Diethylamino	C ₉ H ₁₆ SN ₄ O	200–02	78	681	213	141	–
AK-5	Ethyl	Diethylamino	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ SN ₄ O	185–87	86	681	209	148	+
AK-6	Propyl	Diethylamino	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ SN ₄ O	160–62	68	681	200	140	+
AK-7	Methyl	Dipropylamino	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ SN ₄ O	130–32	72	681	208	144	–
AK-8	Ethyl	Dipropylamino	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ SN ₄ O	148–50	70	1 000	210	110	++
AK-9	Propyl	Dipropylamino	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ SN ₄ O	135–37	69	681	210	115	++
AK-10	Methyl	Dibutylamino	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ SN ₄ O	152–54	75	681	210	140	+
AK-11	Ethyl	Dibutylamino	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ SN ₄ O	100–02	63	1 000	214	139	+
AK-12	Propyl	Dibutylamino	C ₁₅ H ₂₈ SN ₄ O	87–89	59	562	210	144	+
AK-13	Methyl	4-Morpholino	C ₉ H ₁₄ SN ₄ O ₂	160–62	65	>1 000	210	140	+
AK-14	Ethyl	4-Morpholino	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ SN ₄ O ₂	206–08	68	562	216	146	+
AK-15	Propyl	4-Morpholino	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ SN ₄ O ₂	139–41	75	681	210	150	+

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N percentage.

**Administered dose was 1/5th of ALD₅₀; (+)=Moderate effect, (++)=strong effect, (–)=no effect; SMA=spontaneous motor activity, RR=righting reflex.

righting reflexes, spontaneous motor activity (SMA) were recorded following the reported method⁶. Only the compounds showing encouraging effect that is AK-8 and AK-9 were further studied for their effect on pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis in rats following the literature method⁶. The compounds were also studied for anticonvulsant activity using both chemical⁷ and maximal electro-shock method⁸. Results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The ALD₅₀ of compounds were found in the range 562–1000 mg/kg (intraperitoneally). All the compounds showed some depressant effect on the studies on gross behaviour except AK-1, AK-4, AK-7 which showed some stimulant effect. The depressant effects shown by AK-8 and AK-9 were noteworthy and hence pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis study was undertaken. The increase in pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis was found to be 50.81 and 39.48% for AK-8 and AK-9 respectively. None of the compounds was found to be anticonvulsant.

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Synthesis of some 1-Arylthioanilido-4-aryl-3-methyl-6-imino-4,7-dihydropyrazolo-[5,4-d]-1,3-thiazines as Potential Pesticides

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In continuation of our work on fused heterocycles¹ and in view of the activities exhibited by pyrazole² and thiazine³ rings, we thought it of interest to couple these biolabile rings together with the hope

of achieving compounds with better biological activities.

The preparation of 1-arylthioanilido-3-methylpyrazolones (2) can be achieved by heating arylthiosemicarbazides and ethyl acetoacetate by the method of Pathak⁴ with some modification. Condensation of 2 with araldehyde under the Knoevenagel conditions, furnished the desired compounds 3, which on refluxing with thiourea and potassium hydroxide gave the title compounds, 1-arylthioanilido-4-aryl-3-methyl-5-imino-4,7-dihydropyrazolo[5,4-d]-1,3-thiazines (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6 ; 60 MHz) on a Perkin Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Procedure for one typical case for each step has been described. 4-Arylthiosemicarbazides were prepared by the reported method⁵.

1-Arylthioanilido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (2): Substituted-arylthiosemicarbazides (0.1 mol) was heated with ethyl acetoacetate (0.1 mol) for 4–6 h. The products were isolated from ether (R=H, 152°); ν_{max} 1 620 (C=N), 1 230 (C=S) and 3 180 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 2.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.0 (H, s, CH_2CO), 9.4 (1H, s, NH) and 6.4–7.0 (5H, m, ArH).

1-Arylthioanilido-4-aryliden-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (3a–g): A mixture of 1-arylthioanilido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (2; 0.01 mol), the araldehyde (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.011 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in cold water and the resulting solid recrystallised from methanol.

All other compounds were synthesised in similar manner (Table 1): 3b (65%), m.p. 226° (Found: C, 61.79; H, 4.44; N, 11.26. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$ requires: C, 62.12; H, 4.63; N, 11.44%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 410 (OH), 3 180 (NH), 1 630 (C=O), 1 530 (C=N), 1 230 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ 2.2 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.5 (1H, s, C=CH), 6.7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) and 9.4 (1H, s, NH).

1-Arylthioanilido-4-aryl-3-methyl-6-imino-4,7-dihydropyrazolo[5,4-d]-1,3-thiazines (4a–g): A mixture of 1-arylthioanilido-4-aryliden-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01 mol), potassium hydroxide (0.02 mol) and thiourea (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 3–4 h in methanol. After evaporating the solvent, it was then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: 4b (76%), 212° (Found: C, 56.10; H, 4.08; N, 16.24. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 56.47; H, 4.47; N, 16.47%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 410 (OH), 3 190 (NH), 1 530 (C=N) and 1 230 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ 2.2 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.6 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.9 (1H, s, S-CH), 6.4–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 7.6 (2H, h, NH) and 9.2 (1H, s, C=NH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 and 4*

Compd. no	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	142	72	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$
3b	H	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	226	65	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$
3c	2-OH	3-NO ₂	142	60	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$
3d	4-OH	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	168	66	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$
3e	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	202	70	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2\text{Cl}$
3f	4-OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂	179	75	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2\text{Cl}_2$
3g	4-OCH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	185	64	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$
4a	H	H	156	67	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$
4b	H	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	212	76	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$
4c	2-CH ₃	3-NO ₂	95	77	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$
4d	4-CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	146	73	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$
4e	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	218	78	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$
4f	4-OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂	178	75	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$
4g	4-OCH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	165	61	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Biological screening :

Antifungal activity : Antifungal activity of a few representative compounds was performed against *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* using agar growth technique⁶. The compounds in general showed marginal inhibition except compounds 4b, 4e and 4f which exhibited good inhibition of the growth of fungal colony against all strains used. All these three have at least one OCH_3 group amalgamated with either a OH group or one or two chloro group at the phenyl ring. The activity of the compound 4f (90% at 200 ppm) was nearly comparable with dithane M-45 (100% at 200 ppm). Hence, further screening of this compound on wider range of fungi as well as with higher dilution is in progress.

Herbicidal activity : Seeds of the test weeds, e.g. *Amaranthus viridis*, *Polygonum lapathifolium* and *Echinochloa crusgalli* and crops, viz. corn and wheat were planted in square pots. The planted seeds were treated with each test compound. The concentration of compound was 15 g/a with Tween-20

used at a concentration of 100 ppm as a spreader. The treated pots were maintained at 30° in a green house. After four weeks the herbicidal activity of each compound against each weed and their phytotoxicity against crops were evaluated. The herbicidal rating score (from 0~5) was based on visual observation. Zero means no significant effect on seedling growth while 5 means seedling death.

Herbicidal activity data (not shown) indicate that all the test compounds have moderate to low activity towards weeds but quite safe towards crops. Although, various toxophoric groups and structures have been combined in the titled molecules with a hope of achieving compounds of better biocidal potency, the results are not very encouraging. This indicates that the activity of any compound may not necessarily be related to the numerical sum of all toxophores present in the molecule.

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Synthesis of some New Pyrazolinone Azo Dyes

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THE importance of pyrazolinones in the field of dyes is well-known¹. Almost all pyrazolinone dyes are azo dyes having an aryl azo group substituted at the 4-position of a 2-pyrazolin-5-one. A search

of the literature reveals that no work has been reported so far, on the pyrazolinones in which a naphthyl ring is present at the N¹ position. The present work was therefore undertaken to synthesise a number of pyrazolinone azo dyes with better dyeing characteristics. They have been prepared from the appropriate aryl hydrazones of ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate and their subsequent cyclo-condensation with *N*-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide. The pyrazolinones have also been examined for their dyeing characteristics on wool, cotton and polyester using two different mordants, namely chromium sulphate and copper sulphate.

Experimental

The precursors, aryl hydrazones of ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate² and *N*-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide³ were prepared by the reported method.

The condensation of substituted aryl hydrazones with *N*-2-naphthyl malonamic acid hydrazide was brought about by refluxing an equimolecular mixture of the alcoholic solution of the reactants in the presence of few drops of glacial acetic acid for 0.5–3 h. The resulting brightly coloured products were purified by washing repeatedly with hot ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G plates in 10% methanol-benzene.

Condensation of N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide with ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-(2-methyl)-phenylhydrazone. Formation of 4-(2-methyl)phenylhydrazono-N¹-2-naphthylaminomalonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one: A mixture of ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-(2-methyl)phenylhydrazone (1 g, 1 mol) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) and an ethanolic solution of *N*-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide (0.96 g, 1 mol) was refluxed for 45 min in the presence of glacial acetic acid (4–5 drops). The resulting yellow solid was purified by washing several times with ethanol. It was identified as 4-(2-methyl)phenylhydrazono-*N*¹-2-naphthylamino malonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.72 g, 42.15%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 67.50; H, 5.07; N, 11.29. C₂₄H₂₁N₃O₃ requires: C, 67.44; H, 4.91; N, 11.24%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 200 (NH), 3 050 (aromatic-CH stretching 2-naphthalene ring), 1 735 (CONH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 560 (–NH–N=) and 1 360 cm⁻¹ (CH₃ bending).

Similarly other 4-(substituted)phenyl hydrazone-*N*¹-2-naphthylaminomalonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared.

Condensation of N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide with ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-(4-bromo)-phenylhydrazone. Formation of 4-(4-bromo)phenylhydrazono-N¹-2-naphthylaminomalonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one: Following the above procedure a dull green solid was obtained (0.12 g, 12.19%), m.p. 220° (Found: N, 14.35. C₂₃H₁₇BrN₃O₃ requires: N, 14.22%). The δ (CDCl₃) 1.55 (3H, CH₃C=N), 4.20 (2H, COCH₂CO), 7.34–7.39 (2H, aromatic and in the vicinity of Br), 7.4–7.5 (4H, aromatic at